

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Temirboyeva Muaddat

19TH CENTURY OF REALISM AND NATURALISM (THEODORE DREISER)

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

2023/MAY

